

Haemorheologic and Fibrinolytic Activities of Pulmonary Tuberculosis Patients in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT

Pulmonary tuberculosis (PTB) is a major infectious disease with very high prevalence in Nigeria which may increase with the incidence of HIV infection. Severe pulmonary tuberculosis is often complicated by deep vein thrombosis (DVT) because of the association between inflammation and haemostatic changes that can result in an acute phase response and a hypercoagulable state. This research was undertaken to provide information on the haemorheologic and fibrinolytic activities of Nigerian pulmonary tuberculosis patients. A total of one hundred pulmonary tuberculosis patients, (fifty two males and forty eight females) aged 15-45 years, attending the tuberculosis clinics at Dr. Lawrence Henshaw Memorial Hospital and University of Calabar Teaching Hospital, Calabar were investigated. Twenty two of these patients were sero-positive for human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) while seventy eight were sero-negative. Seventy apparently healthy subjects, age and gender matched were used as controls. Erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), relative plasma viscosity (RPV), euglobulin lysis time (ELT) and plasma fibrinogen concentration were estimated using standard methods. Results showed significant increase in ESR, RPV, ELT and fibrinogen levels ($P < 0.05$) approaching normal values as therapy progressed. The ESR of the sero-positive tuberculosis subjects was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) when comparison was made with tuberculosis subjects who were sero-negative for HIV. This work has shown abnormal rheology and impaired fibrinolysis in tuberculosis patients. A combination of these two abnormalities may predispose pulmonary tuberculosis patients to thrombosis and vascular complications. For better treatment and monitoring of response to therapy of tuberculosis patients, it is recommended that plasma viscosity, euglobulin lysis time test and fibrinogen concentration should be part of the routine tests.

Keywords: Pulmonary tuberculosis, haemorheology, fibrinolysis, thrombosis.

INTRODUCTION

Tuberculosis (TB) is a disease caused by a closely-related group of organisms which form the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex. These organisms include *M. tuberculosis*, *M. bovis*, *M. africanum*, *M. microfit* and *M. canetti* (1). Tuberculosis (TB) is one of the oldest known diseases and is still a major cause of mortality. TB has many manifestations affecting system and many other organ systems, but it is primarily a pulmonary disease. Nigeria ranks first in Africa and fourth among the 22 high TB burden countries in the world. No fewer than 460,000 cases of tuberculosis are reported annually in Nigeria (2).

The co - infection of pulmonary tuberculosis with human deficiency virus (HIV)

and acquired immune deficiency syndrome (AIDS) has in the recent past compounded the epidemiology, clinical outcome, diagnosis and treatment of the disease worldwide (3).

Anaemia and other haematological changes are part of the clinical problems of PTB patients. Studies have shown that anaemia, raised erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), leukocytosis and neutrophilia with toxic granulation, thrombocytosis, occasional stickiness of platelets and monocytosis are the most common haematological manifestations associated with PTB (4,5). One study showed a significant increase in plasma viscosity and fibrinogen levels and a decrease in platelet count, total white cell count and packed cell volume when compared with values for apparently healthy subjects (6).

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Although much has been reported on haematological changes in Nigerian pulmonary tuberculosis patients, information on the haemorheologic and fibrinolytic activities of these patients is scanty. It was therefore necessary to study the haemorheologic and fibrinolytic activities of pulmonary tuberculosis patients in Nigeria by determining the erythrocyte sedimentation rate, relative plasma viscosity, euglobulin lysis time and plasma fibrinogen concentration.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A total of 100 male and female pulmonary tuberculosis patients aged between 15 to 45 years, attending the Endemic Disease Clinics of the University of Calabar Teaching Hospital and Dr. Lawrence Henshaw Memorial Hospital, Calabar were enrolled for this study. Pulmonary tuberculosis patients were selected based on the presence of the acid-fast bacilli in their sputum smear. With approval from the Ethical Committee of both hospitals, the bio-data and medical history of these patients were obtained from their case notes.

The HIV status of the patients was obtained from their case notes and both HIV sero-positive and sero-negative patients were enrolled. Seventy age and gender-matched apparently healthy individuals (with no history of tuberculosis and HIV infection) were used as control subjects. They were selected from the staff of University of Calabar, University of Calabar Teaching Hospital and residents of Calabar Municipality. Informed consent was sought and obtained from all participants.

Six and a half millilitres of venous blood was collected under aseptic conditions and with minimal stasis from each subject. An aliquot of 4.5ml was added to ethylene tetra acetic acid anticoagulant at a concentration of 1.5mg/ml for erythrocyte sedimentation rate and plasma viscosity, while the remaining 2ml was added to 0.22ml of 3.13% tri-sodium citrate for euglobulin lysis time test and estimation of fibrinogen concentration.

The citrated blood sample was centrifuged at 3000 rev/min for 15 minutes to separate the plasma. The plasma was separated into clean plasma containers. Tests were performed within 3 hours of sample collection and in duplicates. Westergren (7), Reid and Ugwu (8), Haugie (9) and Clauss (10) methods were used for the determination of erythrocyte sedimentation rate, relative plasma viscosity, euglobulin lysis time and plasma fibrinogen concentration respectively.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviation of the various parameters that were analysed. The mean values obtained for erythrocyte sedimentation rate, relative plasma viscosity, euglobulin lysis time and fibrinogen concentration of PTB patients were significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) than control values. A low positive correlation ($r = 0.209$; $p < 0.05$) between relative plasma viscosity and erythrocyte sedimentation rate was observed (Figure 1) for pulmonary tuberculosis patients.

The haemorheologic and fibrinolytic variables of pulmonary tuberculosis patients based on duration of therapy is presented in Table 2. Of the 100 patients studied, 24 were newly diagnosed, 29 had been on treatment for two to eight weeks, 24 for 8 to 20 weeks and 23 for 20 to 32 weeks. The erythrocyte sedimentation rate, relative plasma viscosity and euglobulin lysis time decreased significantly ($p < 0.05$) as therapy progressed. There was no difference ($p > 0.05$) among the mean values obtained for plasma fibrinogen concentration.

The haemorheologic and fibrinolytic parameters of HIV sero-positive and negative pulmonary tuberculosis patients are presented in Table 3. The ESR of the sero-positive patients was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) than that observed for sero-negative patients. The mean values obtained for relative plasma viscosity, euglobulin lysis time and fibrinogen of the positive patients showed no difference ($p > 0.05$), from those of the negative patients.

Table 1: Haemorheologic and fibrinolytic variables of pulmonary tuberculosis patients and control subjects

Subjects	ESR (mm/hr)	RPV	ELT (min)	PFC (g/L)
PTB (n=100)	44.0 ± 40.0	2.16 ± 0.62	227.12 ± 64.08	6.30 ± 2.50
Non-PTB (n=70)	8.0 ± 7.8	1.62 ± 0.31	172.77 ± 48.81	3.17 ± 0.55
<i>P</i> value	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05

Figure 1: Correlation between relative plasma viscosity and erythrocyte sedimentation rate of pulmonary tuberculosis patients.

Table 2: Haemorheologic and fibrinolytic variables of PTB patients based on duration of therapy

Duration of therapy (weeks)	ESR (mm/hr)	RPV	ELT (min)	PFC (g/L)
New (n=24)	67.0 ± 34.0	2.47 ± 0.73	256.46 ± 68.99	7.07 ± 2.65
2-8 (n=29)	48.0 ± 44.0	2.21 ± 0.62	229.86 ± 73.17	6.47 ± 2.43
9-20 (n=24)	36.0 ± 35.0	2.12 ± 0.66	216.29 ± 51.42	5.69 ± 1.97
21-32 (n=23)	26.0 ± 33.0	1.89 ± 0.38	204.35 ± 42.78	5.93 ± 2.54
<i>P</i> value	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05

Table 3: Haemorheologic and fibrinolytic parameters of HIV sero-positive and negative PTB patients

HIV status	ESR(mm/hr)	RPV	ELT(min)	PFC(g/L)
Sero-positive	86.0 ± 42.0	2.11 ± 0.68	226.86 ± 59.27	6.68 ± 2.71
Sero-negative	32.0 ± 30.0	2.18 ± 0.61	227.19 ± 65.37	6.20 ± 2.38
<i>P</i> value	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05

DISCUSSION

Pulmonary tuberculosis (PTB) is a major infectious disease with very high prevalence in developing countries and this is expected to rise with the incidence of HIV infection. Severe pulmonary tuberculosis (PTB) is often complicated by deep vein thrombosis (DVT) because of the association between inflammation and haemostatic changes that can result in an acute phase response and a hypercoagulable state.

The erythrocyte sedimentation rate and relative plasma viscosity of PTB patients obtained in this study were significantly higher than control values. This agrees with previous findings (11,12). ESR is often raised in infections and inflammatory conditions. Increase in ESR and RPV could be attributed to increased production of acute phase proteins often observed in chronic infections and release of proteins by the causative organism into the circulation. This increase in ESR and RPV implies that there is increased rheology of blood in pulmonary tuberculosis. This is confirmed by a low positive correlation ($r=0.209$; $p<0.05$) observed between relative plasma viscosity and erythrocyte sedimentation rate (Figure 1). From this observation, one may suggest that relative plasma viscosity could be used as an index of plasma protein changes which result from inflammation or tissue damage.

The euglobulin lysis time of PTB patients was significantly higher ($p<0.05$) than the control value. A similar finding has been reported (13). A possible explanation is that tuberculosis might enhance the local production and releases of pro-inflammatory cytokines, which in turn reduces fibrinolytic activity. A reduction in fibrinolysis can lead to the development of venous thrombosis in these PTB patients. Also, the fibrinogen concentration of the PTB patients was significantly higher ($p<0.05$) than control value. This may be due to primed vascular endothelium as a result of the interaction between mycobacterial products and the host monocyte-macrophage system, which then

synthesizes large amounts of tissues necrotic factor (TNF-alpha) and interleukin-6 (IL-6) (14,15). These cytokines induce hepatic acute-phase responses that alter levels of coagulation proteins such as fibrinogen (16).

Fibrinogen is an acute-phase reactant which increases greatly in inflammatory and degenerative conditions such as PTB. It has been reported that the risk of deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is significantly higher (four times) in patients with a fibrinogen level over 5g/L (17). In the present study, the mean fibrinogen level obtained for the patients is 6.30g/L. This implies that PTB patients may develop deep vein thrombosis as a result of the hyperfibrinogenaemia and impaired fibrinolysis observed. The rheologic and fibrinolytic activity of PTB patients improves as therapy progresses. Turken and colleagues (18) reported a change in ESR from 77 ± 22 mm/hr to 41 ± 20 mm/hr ($p<0.05$) within 12 weeks of anti-tuberculosis treatment. Also, fibrinogen levels in their study rose during the first two weeks of therapy (7.99 ± 0.63 g/L) and together with related disturbances, corrected within 12 weeks (5.12 ± 0.68 g/L). Famodu and colleagues also reported a significant decrease in plasma fibrinogen and euglobulin lysis time as a consequence of therapy (13). In this study, the ESR decreased significantly from 67.0 ± 34.0 mm/hr for newly diagnosed patients to 26.0 ± 33.0 mm/hr for patients who had been treated for 20-32 weeks ($P<0.05$). Similarly, the relative plasma viscosity decreased significantly from 2.47 ± 0.73 to 1.89 ± 0.38 as therapy progressed.

There was also a significant decrease ($p<0.05$) in the euglobulin lysis time from 256.46 ± 68.99 minutes at diagnosis to 204.35 ± 42.78 minutes at more than 20 weeks of therapy. Fibrinogen levels decreased from 7.07 ± 2.65 g/L for new patients to 5.93 ± 2.54 g/L after 20 weeks of therapy, but this difference was not statistically significant. This finding then confirms that treatment on time reduces the risk of deep vein thrombosis for PTB patients. Of the 100 pulmonary tuberculosis

patients enrolled in this study, 22 were HIV sero-positive, giving a 22% prevalence rate, while 78 were HIV sero-negative. The 22% prevalence rate of HIV co-infection observed in this study is similar to that reported by the National Tuberculosis and Leprosy Control Programme of Nigeria (19). The mean ESR of the positive patients was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) than that of the sero-negative patients. These differences may be due to the impact of HIV infection on the alveolar macrophages thereby enhancing the pathogenesis of pulmonary tuberculosis.

The mean values obtained for relative plasma viscosity, euglobulin lysis time and fibrinogen of the positive patients were similar ($p > 0.05$) to those of the sero-negative patients. It has been established in this study that there is a significant change in blood rheology and fibrinolytic activity of pulmonary tuberculosis patients. While the haemorrhheologic activity of pulmonary tuberculosis patients increased significantly, their fibrinolytic activity reduced significantly thus pre-disposing them to thrombosis and vascular complications. This has far-reaching implications. Venous thrombosis is involved in the pathogenesis of myocardial infarction, cerebrovascular disease and deep vein occlusion. In view of these findings, it may be necessary to determine relative plasma viscosity, euglobulin lysis time and fibrinogen level routinely for all pulmonary tuberculosis patients in order to properly monitor response to therapy and prevent venous thrombosis and its complications.

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